

Correcting caddisfly synonymy created by apophantic declaration (Trichoptera)

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Abstract. Malicky (2018) synonymized *Tinodes karpathos* Oláh, 2015 described from the Karpathos Island, Greece with *Tinodes petaludes* Malicky, 1974 described from the Rhodes Island. On the basis of re-examination of the *T. karpathos* holotype and compared it with the newly collected *T. petaludes* specimens the synonymy of the two species is rejected and *Tinodes karpathos* is reinstated here as a valid species, stat. restit.!

Keywords. Trichoptera, Tinodes, synonymy, Karpathos, Rhodes.

INTRODUCTION

Malicky (2018) has synonymized *Tinodes karpathos* Oláh, 2015 described from the Karpathos Island, Greece with *Tinodes petaludes* Malicky, 1974 described from the Rhodes Island. In his monograph on Greece Caddisflies (Malicky 2005) recorded *T. petaludes* also from Karpathos Island, probably as a misidentification. Based upon the pronounced and distinct divergences we have found and presented here between *T. petaludes* from Rhodes and *T. karpathos* from Karpathos Island it is possible that his records of *Tinodes petaludes* from Chios, Samos and Kos islands (Malicky 2005) are also misidentifications and may represent unknown incipient sibling species.

***Tinodes karpathos* Oláh, 2015 stat. restit.**

(Figures 1–3)

In our original species description we have compared and found *T. karpathos* more close to *T. reisseri* Malicky described from Crete Island. Here, we present a detailed comparison of our *T. karpathos* to *T. petaludes*, the species that Malicky (2018) considered identical with *T. karpathos*.

Having received specimens of *T. petaludes* from two regions of the Rhodes Island we have compared the holotype of *T. karpathos* with these three specimens. The fine genital structure was rather stable at the three available specimens of *T. petaludes*. There are several trait divergences between the synonymized *T. karpathos* and *T. petaludes* detectable even by gross morphology detailed below.

(1) The paraproct-phallic organ complex are entirely different at the two species; the pair of the free digitiform processes of paraproct is armed with a strong terminal spine of megaseta at *T. petaludes*; *T. karpathos* lacks this terminal structure; at *T. petaludes* the phallic organ is armed with eight megasetae subapicad in ventrolateral position on both sides but the number of megasetae is only two at *T. karpathos*; the phallic head is firmly constricted forming a stable shape by the elaborated alveoli lines of megasetae on both side at *T. petaludes* and more loose, more membranous, therefore dilated at *T. karpathos* without such a bracing structure. Documented by molecular genetic studies on *Drosophila* species we have to realize how elaborated genetic background produces a simple shape modification. Several thousand or tens of thousands of sequence loci with complex interactions of epigenetics,

Figure 1–3. Genital organs of *Tinodes petaludes* and *T. karpathos*. 1= Paraproct and phallic organ complex, 2 = basal plate of gonopod, 3= gonopod.

epistasis and pleiotropy determine just a simple curvature on a lobe structure (McNeil *et al.* 2011). We can imagine how complex sequences and their interactions generate and maintain such sophisticated divergences clearly visible between the paraproct and phallic organ complexes of the synonymized two species, *T. petaludes* and *T. karpathos*.

(2) There are divergences in the fine structure of the basal plate of gonopods as well. The dorsal pair of processes is curving deep ventrad at *T. petaludes* and curving more posterad at *T. karpathos*; the basement of the ventral processes with strong apical megaseta is differently shaped; the position and pattern of the serrated lateral ridge on the dorsal processes is also diverged.

(3) There are significant shape divergences on the gonopods; the body of coxopodite is different; the dorsoapical bilobed structure of the coxo-

podite entirely diverged; the shape of harpago is different (Figs. 1–3).

Based on re-examination of the holotype of *T. karpathos* and compared it with newly collected *T. petaludes* specimens, *Tinodes karpathos* is reinstated here as a valid species, **stat. restit.!**

Material examined. *Tinodes karpathos* Oláh, 2015: Holotype: **Greece**, South Aegean, Karpathos regional unit, Esochori, spring and its outlet at Vryssiani church, 125m, N35°37.954', E27°06.600', 12.11.2012, leg. J. Kontschán, D. Murányi (1 male, HNHM). *Tinodes petaludes* Malicky, 1975: **Greece**, South Aegean, Rhodes regional unit, Eleousa, artificial spring lake at the village, 290m, N36°16.370', E28°01.439', 14.11.2012 leg. J. Kontschán, D. Murányi (1 male, HNHM). South Aegean, Rhodes regional unit, Vati, roadside spring E of the village, 75m, N36°03.225', E27°54.486', 08.11.2012 leg. J. Kontschán, D. Murányi (2 males, HNHM).

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